

Skin expansion can produce an illusion of slipperiness

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Abstract. We report a new illusion where a feeling of slipperiness is perceived when the skin is deformed radially upon contact with a surface. We built a tactile device that radially deforms both the index and thumb using soft deformable membranes. The slipperiness sensation is achieved by modulating the rate of expansion, which can be controlled according to the squeezing force applied on the object. We showed preliminary result suggesting that this deformation pattern generates a sensation of slipperiness.

Keywords: Friction perception · Skin stretch · Tactile feedback.

1 Introduction

Humans fundamentally interact with their environment using their sense of touch. Among the range of sensations touch provides, friction stands out as an essential ingredient for delicate grasping [2]. We previously observed that during initial contact with an object, the skin deforms in a radially expanding pattern which magnitude correlates with the perceived friction. It implies that the frictional information is available prior to any lateral movement occurring [3]. While the correlation has been established, the questions of whether this radially expanding deformation pattern directly *causes* the perception of friction remain unexplored.

In this work, we introduce a tactile device equipped with two deformable membranes able to drive skin expansion. We demonstrate that such deformation can indeed produce a sensation of slipperiness. Providing tactile feedback of friction has the potential to significantly enhance the realism of the rendering and improve operators performance in dexterous grasping tasks in tele-robotics.

2 Materials and Methods

The instrumented object was guided on a 8 mm steel shaft (Bosch Rexroth, 400mm) using two linear sleeve bearings to counteract any torques that arise around the fingertip-object contacts (Fig 1A). The final object measures $73 \times 60 \times 100 \text{ mm}^3$ and weights 360 g. A constant force spring is compensating 195 g of the total weight, which makes the object easy to hold with two fingers in a pinch grasp. The surfaces on both sides are made of stretchable silicone bonded on six resin-printed sliders with primer. The latter use pins that slide in circular slots on a central rotating wheel (Fig 1B). This device can provide a skin stretch in a radially expanding manner, and a constant linear velocity can be

Fig. 1. **A.** Schematic of the experimental setup. The object was equipped with deformable membranes on both sides, and was free to move along and around the linear guide. **B.** Rotating wheel mounted on a frame with six sliders to generate the skin expansion. **C.** Radial displacement of the sliders as a function of the angle α . **D.** Control of the angle α as a function of the grip force applied by the participant.

achieved with a constant rotational velocity (Fig 1C). The divergence of the deformation of the silicon following a linear relation with the linear displacements of the sliders, this device can allow to control the amount of diverging skin as a function of the normal force with the angle of rotation of the wheel α (Fig 1D).

The study was approved by the ethics committee of the MIT (IRB 2310001135). One right-handed participant was asked to accomplish 50 testing trials. In each trial, the participant should casually lift, hold and replace the object at the same position using the tips of their index finger and opposing thumb of their right hand. Participant encountered five different conditions, presented 10 times each, given by the angle of rotation α shown in Fig 1D. The reference stimulus was assigned as the lowest angle and produces the lowest skin deformation divergence. The protocol followed a 2-alternative forced choice procedure such that after two lifts, the participant was asked to answer in which one the object surfaces felt the most slippery.

The vertical position of the object was measured with an incremental rotary encoder (Taiss 600P/R) linked with a capstan transmission. The grip forces were acquired with a strain gauge (SingleTact) placed on the thumb side (Figure 2A). A Raspberry pi camera was embedded on the index finger side to measure the skin expansion at 30 Hz (Fig 2B).

3 Results

The probability to identify the highest expansion as the most slippery stimuli increases with the control angle α (Figure 2C). The participant reaches 75% of correct identification for $\alpha = 0.27$ rad, corresponding to a divergence of skin deformation of $10 \mu\text{m}/\text{mm}$ approximately. Interestingly, the maximum grip force during the lift increases with the control angle α (Figure 2D), suggesting that the sensorimotor control of grip acts as if there was a reduction of friction.

Fig. 2. **A.** Vertical position of the object and normal force applied by the participant during the lift. **B.** The radial expansion of the index finger skin increase with the normal force. **C.** Probability to identify the largest expansion as the most slippery stimulus as a function of the control angle α . **D.** Maximum of the grip force as a function of the control angle α .

4 Conclusion and Future work

In this paper, we present a novel tactile device able to provide a continuous radial expansion of the finger skin during a grasping task. Unlike previous devices that employ a pin-based approach to drive deformation pattern for tactile feedback, which reduces the cutaneous interaction to a point [1], our device utilizes deformable membranes to produce continuous spatially-distributed sensations. The preliminary user study demonstrated the human ability to perceive this radial expansion as an increase in surface slipperiness. Future work will focus on optimizing the device to maximize its effects for various users.

Acknowledgments. This study was funded by the European Commission (Marie Curie grant project ReTouch).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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